

How Does Discrimination Affect the US Department of Health and Human Services through Political, Scientific, and Economic Lenses?

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In the United States, we are striving for equal access to healthcare, but discrimination is a reality faced by many, leaving us to question the profound impact it has on the welfare of marginalized communities. The US Department of Health and Human Services is an executive branch department in the US federal government that ensures Americans have access to high-quality healthcare and other social services. A question emerges when acknowledging the implications of prejudice, bias, and inequality on the government's policies and the lives of those it serves: How does discrimination affect the US Department of Health and Human Services? This is a pivotal question to explore because equity within the government is responsible for promoting the health and well-being of all Americans. The first notable topics from the perspective of minorities are medical mistrust and sexual minorities having lessened access to healthcare, and lastly, through the perspective of the HHS, contributions, and comprehension concerning discrimination.

Medical mistrust is a prevalent repercussion of discrimination towards racial and socioeconomic minorities in the US Department of Health and Human Services. Mohsen Bazargan, a medical sociologist, explains that people more likely to perceive discrimination have greater mistrust, and experience poorer health outcomes (Bazargan et al). This discrimination is often directed towards individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds or who have had negative experiences with the healthcare system previously. Studies show people who experience racial discrimination are 25% more likely to doubt the efficacy of medicine. Seth C.

Kalichman, a professor who dedicates his research to preventing the spread of HIV and AIDS, revealed death rates for blacks living with HIV to be 13% higher than for whites (qtd. in Kalichman). This is relevant to the administration of antiretroviral therapy (ART) for HIV/AIDS. Medical mistrust was significantly associated with ART adherence, as were beliefs about medication necessity, which is causing a higher number of HIV infections in other races (Kalichman et al). Demographic data further supports the link between medical mistrust and ART adherence.

The sexual minority population evidently has inferior access to health care. Frances Grimstad discusses the recent ruling of *Dobbs v Jackson Women's Health Organization* which determined individuals who can become pregnant now have abortion limitations. Public discussion about abortion access, however, has focused on the erosion of women's fundamental rights, mischaracterizing all of those affected by the court ruling (Grimstad et al). The use of gender-inclusive language is detrimental to women's rights regarding the importance of basic reproductive health care access (Grimstad et al). The US Department of Health and Human Services has also implemented a rule on conscience rights. Christiane S. Cardoza, author of an article published in 2019 highlighted that the rule will promote religious freedom protections for healthcare entities refusing to participate in certain procedures (qtd. in Cardoza). While implicit, the rule offers protection to providers who might refuse to treat LGBT individuals. (Cardoza et al). Based on available evidence, the perspective of minorities is compared to that of the HHS in they are consistent through the identifiable issues regarding discrimination.

The US Department of Health and Human Services plays a major role in the impact discrimination has on minorities' access to healthcare. The Pregnancy Act provides that discrimination on the basis of pregnancy, childbirth, or related medical conditions is a type of unlawful sex discrimination (*U.S. Department of Commerce*, 5 Aug. 2019). The PDA addresses the issue at hand, rights are not being taken into account when employers are working with pregnant women. Brianna L. Eaton, a transactional attorney provides, as an example, an employer at Walmart told a woman being pregnant was not an excuse when she was unable to lift heavy trays at full-term (Eaton 7). Reverting to the topic of medical mistrust, the HHS issued a rule to rescind the Bush midnight provider refusal rule because of its potential effect on limiting access to reproductive health treatment, including emergency services and treatment for patients with HIV and AIDS (qtd. in Cardoza). Additionally, the type of health insurance coverage and perceived quality of health care affect the quality of service. Yong-Rock Hong, an author of a research paper discussing data collected from multiple studies, observed being white was associated with a better-perceived quality of healthcare services among the privately insured, further suggesting minority ethnic groups experienced more discrimination (Hong et al). Furthermore, being privately insured increases the quality of health care than publicly which is more affordable. The new rule conflicts with the Affordable Care Act, which prohibits various forms of discrimination in covered health programs or activities. (Section 1557). The HHS appears to be making efforts to target the issue and help solve the problem.

The newfound significance of the topic provides a deeper display of how discrimination can undermine the HHS's effectiveness in delivering essential services. The HHS is

implementing rules that substantially affect the healthcare received by minorities, but minorities seem to have presented a stronger argument because available healthcare is determined by the actions taken by the HHS. The possible solutions to prevent these negative outcomes could include implementing anti-discrimination policies to help raise awareness among health service workers. Additionally, the HHS should prioritize diversity in its workforce and leadership positions, as diverse perspectives can lead to more effective improvements. In conclusion, providing quality healthcare for all Americans will better the overall well-being and productivity of the population.

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